

**THE MAIN ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING
PUBLICPRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM**

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Abstract: The economic essence of public-private partnership is that public organizations and private companies combine their resources and experience to implement certain projects, which allows them to reduce the costs of project implementation and increase efficiency. In this article, the main advantages, disadvantages and development trends of the use of public-private partnership in the field of tourism are shown separately.

Key words: public-private partnership, project, resource, cooperation, investment, monitoring, control, private organizations, risk, private investor.

Our country has many of its own various historical and architectural monuments with its climate and rapid development attracting the attention of the whole world is coming Uzbekistan for centuries Great Silk Road trade, merchants and travelers, linguists and missionaries, on the path of invaders and conquerors was located. Meanwhile, Uzbekistan is an initiative, culture, history, to traditional and exotic countries fascinating tourism for those interested is becoming one of the directions.

Tourism potential in our country development is one of the important factors is spinning. In later years increasingly integrated economy increasing, systematic international relations that the tourism sector is developing steadily as a result of its improvement can be seen. The economy in the context of innovative development tourism industry in the national economy its position and influence are also increasing more and more. Because tourism is one of the most profitable industries is considered one. Public-private partnerships are different can be done in the form of eg joint ventures, concession contracts, participation in projects and others.

Tourism from public private partnership the tourism sector by using the sector radical development and our country increasing the volume of tourist flow possible Thanks to public private partnership underdeveloped travel agencies more within the framework of state programs expanding the flow of investments to them it is necessary to direct. Tourism potential in developed countries today is growing rapidly. In our

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country and several reforms in the field of tourism was held. In particular, from 350 in Uzbekistan More hotels accept tourists in accordance with international standards providing services. 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Uzbektourism" national by decree company was established. "Uzbek tourism "The main task and purpose of tourism implementation of state policy in the field and national model of tourism development is to create. Also, a national company all those working in our profession activities of tourist organizations Coordinates all of tourism the development of directions encourages, with personnel issues deals with the material and technical base formation and industry infrastructure attracts investment flow to its development. Besides tourist potential of Uzbekistan UNWTO in support in Tashkent under the leadership of International "Silk Road Tourism" the fair is also very important. The main purpose of this fair is tourism Uzbek and foreign in the field unite experts, between them further professional close cooperation consists of expansion. To date this is an international fair in Central Asia place as one of the largest exhibitions received.

Summary

Legendary past, Silk the historical and engineering heritage of the road, wonderful landscapes of nature, local, passed down from generation to generation crafts, people's hospitality and tourists with human values this is amazing and fascinating along with making them happy from all corners of Uzbekistan attracts people that is why we state the potential of tourism in the future more through private partnerships our development and tourism in the future we need to increase the weight of companies.

References:

1. Dmitrievsky Yu.D. Tourist areas of the world. Smolensk, 2000. 224 p.
2. Kolotova E. V. Recreational resource science: Textbook. allowance. - M.: RMATS. [1, p. 92-93]
3. Karpov G.A., Khoreva L.V. Economics and tourism management activities. St. Petersburg, 2011. 268 p. [2.p.135]
4. Koroleva N.V. Simulation modeling of tourism development directions in recreational areas of the region. Maykop, 2007. 164 p.
5. Richards, G. (1996) Cultural Tourism in Europe. CABI, Wallingford. [1, p. 45]